

THE ROLE OF SYNCHRONOUS TRANSLATION IN LITERARY TEACHING

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ANNOTATION: Synchronous translation is of great scientific and professional nature, and since it is usually used in official international conferences, synchronous translation requirements are extremely high. Synchronous translation requires that the translator listens and discerns the original language at the time it is spoken, and can quickly predict, comprehend, remember, and direct the original language, relying on thematic knowledge.

Key words: synchronous translation, conferences, interpreter, conference translation, seminars, Russian, English, French, Spanish, German, technology-based translation

Introduction. As we know, there are several criteria for dividing translation into certain groups. The following classification of the well-known scientist Z.G. Proshina classifies the types of translation based on several criteria:

- 1) Depending on who is doing the translation: a) human translation; b) computer translation;
- 2) By the form of speech: a) written translation; b) oral translation (on-sight translation); c) oral translation of oral speech;
- 3) according to the source perception method: a) visual translation; b) audio translation;
- 4) according to the time value between source comprehension and translation: a) consecutive translation; b) synchronous translation;
- 5) Depending on the number of languages used: a) one-sided; b) two-way translation;
- 6) By the direction of translation: a) direct (to native); b) counter translation (to a foreign language);

7) By the use of translation methods: a) writing translation; b) word-for-word translation.

Literature Review. In Uzbekistan, we can also note significant studies on the direction of synchronous translation. Among them O. Muminov, I. Gafurov, G. Salomov, N. Kambarov and other scholars' textbooks on translation studies synchronous translation, its features and methods, problems and difficulties arising during the process. However, it should be noted that, these problems have not been considered as a conceptual problem. The famous scientist N.A.Shermuhammedova describes the conceptual problem as follows: Conceptual problems relate to a large number of previous data, and to regulate and interpret them, to produce consequences and to formulate hypotheses, and consider the elimination of contradictions in accordance with the logical consistency requirements. Therefore, it is advisable to analyze the data obtained earlier in the study of these problems and to cover the issue on the basis of logical sequence.

Methods and analysis. Synchronous translation (Greek "sunkhronos", "sun" - "joint", "chronos" - "time"), which is the subject of our research, is a time-dependent translation. It is a translation in which the interpreter translates the speech of the speaker to one or two people at the same time. The translator is currently sitting in the cabin, listening to the speaker through special headphones and then translating it through the microphone. Participants listen in the conference room through headphones. This type of translation is also called "conference translation" because it is widely used in conferences. In addition to being widely used in international conferences, synchronous translation is also widely used in diplomatic activities, negotiations and meetings, trade events, media, training and education courses, television, international arbitration and many other areas. Unlike this type of translation, a synchronous translation method is most commonly used in events that use only two working languages, which are relatively small. For example, it can be used in diplomatic meetings, bilateral negotiations, expeditions, small-scale discussion agreements, reporter interviews, litigation, banquet speeches. There are six official languages in the UN, Arabic, Chinese, English, French, Russian and Spanish. These six languages are equally effective, and delegates can choose any language during the speech. The working language of the UN Secretariat daily is English and French. Any official UN

conferences are held in six languages, and official papers and key note speeches are also published in six languages. Speaking of synchronous translation, you need to have an idea of the entire system that comprises it. Headphones and a translator's microphone, as well as a set of headphones or portable speakers, depending on the number of participants that need translation. During the conference, synchronous translators wear sound insulation headphones in a separate room to keep their voices silent. With the sound amplifier, the translation is delivered to the listener. Synchronous technology-based translation is traditionally organized by events involving large numbers of people and events in a large conference room or auditorium, such as conferences, seminars, presentations. In practice there are three types of synchronous translation:

1) Memorable synchronous translation (listening). In this case, the interpreter receives the speaker's continuous speech through the headphones and blocks the translation as the information falls. This is the most common and the most difficult.

2) Synchronous translation with or without preparation. The synchronous interpreter receives a pre-written text of the speaker's speech and translates it according to the material presented.

3) Synchronizing previously translated text. The synchronous interpreter reads the text already prepared after the speaker's speech. In some cases, the speaker may need to make adjustments if he or she avoids the original text during the talk. Unlike consecutive translation, the synchronous translation has the following advantages:

- The speaker's speech is interrupted. This allows the speaker to keep the audience focused and to react to the reaction and mood of the audience.

- The time spent to the event is almost halved as compared to the use of consistent translation.

- For the convenience of participants, learning a foreign language is not uncommon at this time, and many participants prefer to listen to reports in a foreign language. In the consistent translation, the speaker stops and continues with the translation, which irritates the participants.

Discussion. As a form of synchronous translation, its greatest feature is high efficiency, with an average of 3-4 seconds between the original text and the speech. Maximum up to 10 seconds.

Consequently, the speaker is guaranteed continuous speech, does not have any outside influence on the speaker's opinion and does not interrupt his speech. This will allow the audience to understand the speech as a whole. As a result, synchronous translation is now the most common method of translation in the world. Currently, 95% of international meetings are used in synchronous translation at conferences. At the same time, synchronous translation is of great scientific and professional nature, and since it is usually used in official international conferences, synchronous translation requirements are extremely high. Synchronous translation requires that the translator listens and discerns the original language at the time it is spoken, and can quickly predict, comprehend, remember, and direct the original language, relying on thematic knowledge. According to the decision of the International Synchronous Interpreters' Association, a translator can achieve only 80% of the speaker's speech content. Most people have a very fast pace of speech and they always care about the content of their speech, even when they are speaking. In addition, people complicate translation with various local accents. In these cases, the synchronous interpreter will have to move his or her own treasure of knowledge and act according to their experience. There are not many speakers who can deliberately talk about a synchronized interpreter. This puts very high demands on the nature of the specialist. Today, even if computer-translators are widely available, there is a great need for synchronous translators and their providers. Synchronous translation is a much more complex process. It is important that the interpreter focuses on the tone, pace, and stylistic elements of the speech as well as many other (non-computer) aspects of the speech. Otherwise, there will be a lot of confusion between the speaker and the listener. There are two schemes of synchronous translation in international conferences. The first scheme is a direct translation scheme used by the United Nations and its specialized agencies. In this scheme, the number of booths corresponds to the number of session or working languages of the session. For example, the five official languages adopted at UN meetings include the following language booths: English, French, Russian, Spanish and Chinese. At each meeting, there is a team of translators in each booth who must provide translation from the four languages left in their cabins. It is assumed that this rule is not always practical, that is, a synchronous interpretation is performed by a translator in his native language. Usually 2

translators are attached to the cabin. It is assumed that their common language combination will translate directly from the four languages into their native language. For example, a translator in one Russian cabin should speak English, French, Spanish and the other English and Russian. Similar rules apply to all other cabins. The second scheme of organizing synchronous translation is called "leading language translation" or "schema with the chief translator." This scheme is mainly used in socialist countries. Under this scheme, one of the working languages of the conference (in English) is declared as the leading, main language. This means that the number of booths is always less than the number of working languages of the conference or congress. With five working languages - Russian, English, French, Spanish, and German, the conference will have only four cabins: Russian, French, Spanish, and German. If the speaker is in English, a team of translators (usually three people) will translate English into their cabin in each booth, and if the speaker is speaking in that foreign language, they will translate from English into English. In the second case, the remaining three cabins translate into their cabin language not directly from the speaker's speech, but from the English speech of the first, "main" or "leading" cabin. The leading cabin translator becomes the "main translator". Thus, in all cases, when a speaker does not speak in English, a two-step translation into other foreign languages is made. Any cabin, that is, any translator can become a "major translator" at any time during the conference. They translate from one foreign language into English, or one from English into another. Before proceeding to comparing one or another scheme of synchronous translation, it is necessary to understand the concept of language combination in synchronous translation. Under the concept of combination, we understand a translation performed by a synchronist from one original (IT) language to another specific translation language (TT). For example, translation from English into Russian. In this case the translator is working in the English-Russian combination. One of the official requirements for a synchronous interpreter in the United Nations is to work in more than two language combinations. As a rule, the translation of these two foreign languages into their native language must be compatible. The translator works in convergent combinations to work in accordance with the UN scheme. In the second scheme, the translator works in reciprocal or reversible combinations. The disadvantages of the two-step translation scheme are the following:

- 1) Loss of volume and accuracy of transmitted information;
- 2) Any error in the translation made by the "Chief Translator" is inevitable for all channels
- 3) The "Chief Translator" will suffer additional difficulties, such as the need to revise his translation not only by the receiver but also by other translators, which has a significant effect on the tone and pace of the translation;
- 4) it is often difficult to switch from one type of job to another;
- 5) serious technical problems are sometimes caused by the need for frequent channel switching, especially when switching short sentences. (e.g. during a meeting a "round table");

The one-step scheme adopted by the UN and several other international organizations is intended for each synchronist to translate two or more foreign languages into their own language. This scheme should, in theory, provide a higher quality translation. However, it should be noted that a one-step scheme can only be used in a small number of working language conferences. The motto of synchronized translation is "only success and no error". Usually, when the conference is over, all of the organizers, the chairmen of the assemblies, the experts and the delegates will be thanking the synchronous interpreter. If the translator's work is well done, they will be commended and some will even invite you to cooperate with them the next time. If the ST is extremely distressed, then in the conference room, you will be able to observe a variety of reactions, such as depression, divergence, and speech. Even the smallest elements in the ST process cannot be ignored. The translate cabin's microphone is extremely sensitive, and the volume of movement in the cabin should be very quiet. Even the pages of the book, the slow silence of the large earrings worn by a female interpreter, can be a great hit in the ears of the audience.

This article describes the image of imaginary diseases in the stories of Edgar Allan Poe and the reasons for writing about diseases. The allegory and symbolism by depicting the Red Death.¹

¹ Akhmedovna, B. M., & Shakhnoza, B. (2022). The Image of Disease in Edgar Allan Poe's "The Masque of the Red Death". *Pindus Journal of Culture, Literature, and ELT*, 2(1), 19-22.

The article is devoted to the analysis of the *The Magic Hat* book, written by popular Uzbek writer Khudoyberdi Tukhtaboyev, from the position of classification elements introduced by the famous Russian philosopher, literary critic and scholar Mikhail Mikhailovich Bakhtin.²

The depiction of natural landscapes given in works of art is one of the factors that demonstrate the creative artistic skill.³

В современной методике так же, как и много лет назад, актуальной и нерешенной до сих пор остается проблема поиска и выбора наиболее эффективных и рациональных методов преподавания иностранных языков, соответствующих современным условиям обучения и отвечающих требованиям стандартов современного образования.⁴

The article describes in detail the basics of translation theory, the object of research, and the methods of analysis of translation theory.⁵

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.⁶

This lesson plan format moves from teachers to centered student. In order to keep this standard lesson plan format from becoming monotonous, it is seminal to memorize that there are a number of variations that can be applied within the various segments of the lesson plan format.⁷

This article deals with the analysis of pastiche in literature, particularly in "The Lightning Thief" by American author Rick Riordan. The research identifies pastiche as a term, which is

² Kadirova, N. A. (2020). ANALYSIS OF TRANSFORMATION MOTIFS IN THE MAGIC HAT BOOK BY KHUDOYBERDI TUKHTABOYEV, THROUGH THE PRISM OF MIKHAIL BAKHTIN'S THEORIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 405-408.

³ Kabilova, F., & Tokhirovna, T. K. English Translation of Abdullah Qadiri's Novel "Days Gone by" and Its Reflection Skills. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(10), 304-306.

⁴ Абдуллаева, Л. С., Самадова, С. А., & Махмурова, М. (2014). Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. *Наука. Мысль: электронный периодический журнал*, (6), 73-76.

⁵ Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.

⁶ Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

⁷ Nodirovna, N. N., & Temirovna, P. M. (2022). Principles of designing lesson plans for teaching ESL or EFL. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 5, 10-12.

applied to a literary work that is a broad mixture of things-such as themes, concepts, and characters-imitated from different literary works.⁸

This article is devoted to the study of Somerset Maugham's short story "The Book Bag". It mainly focuses on the analysis of moral and immoral issues, emphasizing to the matter of incest and its fatal outcomes.⁹

The relevance of speech and culture in the present day is considered important in linguistics and its areas of study are becoming more and more comprehensive day by day.¹⁰

В этой статье дается краткий обзор антропонимов, их функций статуса, который они получают от этих, и их специфики.¹¹

The article is about the development of the Soviet era of Uzbek educational dictionary. The educational dictionaries created during this period served mainly to teach Russian in national schools.¹²

This article deals with the description of synonyms in the explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek language published in different periods, the systematic description of the similarities and differences between the explanations of synonyms in the publications.¹³

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines the right of citizens to vote and to be elected, the foundations of the national electoral system, the basis of which are the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and

⁸ Khabibullaeva, R. M. (2020). ANALYSIS OF PASTICHE IN THE NOVEL "THE LIGHTNING THIEF" BY RICK RIORDAN. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 958-961.

⁹ Куницька, І. (2014). Роман-біографія як жанровий різновид модерністського роману (С. Моем Місяць і мідяки). *Сучасні літературознавчі студії*, (11), 342-348.

¹⁰ NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).

¹¹ Орипова, К. (2022). ОНОМАСТИЧЕСКАЯ ПРОБЛЕМА НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНОСТИ ВО ФРАНЦУЗСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz)*, 8(8). извлечено от http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/4712

¹² Bakhridinova, B. M. (2020). HISTORY OF CREATING FIRST BILINGUAL AND REGULATORY EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES IN UZBEK LANGUAGE. *Scientific reports of Bukhara State University*, 4(1), 147-181.

¹³ Rustamovna, M. G. (2020). Presenting synonyms in the explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek language. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 6, 117-120.

ratification by Uzbekistan, constituting the principles of democracy, including independence, legitimacy, transparency and fairness, enshrined and recognized in other international legal instruments.¹⁴

This article discusses an attitude to women in the past and the interpretation of the image of women in the works of some writers.¹⁵

Conclusion. Currently, there are a number of international organizations accrediting translators in the world. Of these, the International Association of Conference Interpreters (IACI) was established in 1953 and is widely recognized as the highest professional interpreter of the conference translators. There is no need to take any exams to become a member of IACI. This requires two years of full-time work as an interpreter at a full-time conference, and a masters degree in Translation Studies. In addition, more than 3 translators with over 5 years of experience will be required to guarantee. The guarantor must work in a team with an interpreter applying for membership. The European Commission's Interpretation and Conference Service (JICS) was established in Brussels, Belgium. The procedure for selecting translators is as follows: First, the best of each region will be selected, which will require oral translators 25 to 30 years of age, 3 years of experience, and a bachelor's degree in English. Preliminary exams, the second round of exams, and interviews are required. In fact, the largest oral translation team in the world is not on the UN, but on the EU Committee. The Committee has about 500 synchronous interpreters hired by the headquarters of the translators. The Committee of the European Union, in particular, emphasizes the quality of the language and its fluency. Thus, it took almost a century for the synchronous translation to take shape from its initial use to its present appearance.

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¹⁴ Tolibjonovich, M. T., & Toxirjonovich, S. D. (2021). The Institutional Mechanisms Of The Development Of The Electoral System In Uzbekistan. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 7(8), 4378-4384.

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